

Studies on the Formation and Semiconducting Properties of Lithium and Potassium Niobates

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Manuscript received 21 March 1978, revised 25 July 1978, accepted 4 August 1978

The formation of lithium and potassium niobates have been studied in the temperature range of 600-1000° by heating niobium pentoxide and corresponding alkali carbonates in different proportions. Following niobates have been prepared :

$\text{Li}_2\text{O.Nb}_2\text{O}_5$, $2\text{Li}_2\text{O.Nb}_2\text{O}_5$, $3\text{Li}_2\text{O.Nb}_2\text{O}_5$ and $\text{K}_2\text{O.Nb}_2\text{O}_5$

The electrical conductivity of these niobates were measured in the range of 313-523°K. By measuring the Seebeck coefficients types of conduction in the compounds were ascertained.

GREENER *et al*¹ measured the electrical conductivity of $\alpha\text{-Nb}_2\text{O}_5$ single crystals and sintered specimens under a constant oxygen pressure and in the temperature range 573-1173°K. They observed exponential temperature dependence with an activation energy of 1.65 eV in both the cases. Greener and Hirthe² measured the electrical conductivity of $\alpha\text{-Nb}_2\text{O}_5$ after prior reduction in 10^{-6} atm of air, from 350-1150°K, for both single crystals and sintered specimens. The conductivity of single crystals was found to be exponentially dependent with an activation energy of 0.91 eV in the range of 1150°-650°K and 0.2 eV in the range of 650°-350°K. The electrical conductivity of sintered specimen was also found to be exponentially dependent on temperature, but only a single activation energy was obtained over the entire temperature range. This activation energy was dependent on defect concentration and varied from 1.0 eV for the smallest degree of reduction to almost zero at the highest degree of reduction where the behaviour was essentially that of a degenerate semiconductor.

On the other hand, Chen and Swalin³ re-examined the temperature dependence of electrical conductivity using $\alpha\text{-Nb}_2\text{O}_5$ single crystals in an oxygen pressure range of 1 atm to 10^{-6} atm and temperature range of 873-1623°K. From the temperature dependence of the conductivity at constant oxygen pressure it was observed that, at high temperatures the activation energy is 1.4 eV, whereas below 1073°K it is 0.4 eV.

Jander and Frey⁴ studied the reactions of Nb_2O_5 with various oxides BaO, SrO, CaO, MgO, ZnO, CuO, K_2O and Na_2O . Evnalova and Rashkovich⁵ prepared lithium metaniobate by baking stoichiometric mixture of Li_2CO_3 and Nb_2O_5 at 1000° for 2-3 hours and determined the domain structure of crystals. Hilton Robert⁶ prepared lithium niobate

by sintering Li_2CO_3 and Nb_2O_5 for 12-15 hr at 950° only and obtained single crystals at 1300°. Dielectric and conductivity measurements were made simultaneously by Deshmukh and Ingle⁷ for single crystals of potassium niobates. Roitberg *et al*⁸ measured the pyroelectric and electrical conductivity of lithium metaniobate single crystals in the range of 293-523°K. Novik *et al*⁹ measured thermoelectric effects in lithium metaniobate whereas Cermak Karel¹⁰ studied optical properties in the near ultraviolet spectral region. Large single crystals of lithium niobate were grown using an automated puller by Zydzik G¹¹. Byer *et al*¹² found the use of lithium metaniobate in electro-optical switch and second harmonic generation. Preparation of pure potassium metaniobate has been reported by Arnold Reisman *et al*¹³. They observed the formation of potassium metaniobate at 1075° in one hour. Impurity segregations and their interaction with domains and dislocations in potassium metaniobate single crystals were studied by Mishra and Ingle¹⁴.

The present investigation was, therefore, undertaken with a view to study systematically the formation of alkali niobates between 600°-1000°.

The semiconducting properties of these prepared niobates were studied by measuring electrical conductivity and Seebeck coefficients.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of B. D. H. AnalaR quality. α , β and $\gamma\text{-Nb}_2\text{O}_5$ were obtained by heating amorphous Nb_2O_5 at 1200, 1000 and 600° respectively^{15, 16}. The transformation of these forms was confirmed by Differential Thermal Analysis. Several mixtures were prepared by weighing accurately niobium pentoxide and the alkali carbonates in different proportions. These were mixed separately in an agate pestle and mortar, transferred into platinum or Porcelain crucibles and heated for a fixed interval of time (3 hr).

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The heated mass was taken out, powdered well and weighed. Weighed quantity of the reacted mass was transferred into a conical flask and washed with CO₂ free hot water till free of unreacted oxides. Pure niobate thus obtained was dried at 110-120° for 24 hours and then cooled in a desiccator containing KOH.

A weighed quantity of the washed product was decomposed by known strength of HCl acid and alkali oxides were estimated by standard methods. Hydrated niobium pentoxide was precipitated by adding ammonium hydroxide at pH between 7-8. The precipitate was filtered, washed free of chloride ions, ignited and weighed. The results are reported in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Formation of Lithium and Potassium niobates as f(T).
 ○ refers to Li and □ refers to K compound; Time of heating 3 hr.

× = no compound formation
 1 = metaniobates M₂O.Nb₂O₅
 2 = pyroniobates 2Li₂O.Nb₂O₅
 3 = orthoniobates, 3Li₂O.Nb₂O₅

For conductivity measurements¹⁷ pellets were prepared by compressing well powdered pure niobate at a pressure of 2 × 10⁷ kg per sq. m. Pellets thus obtained were coated with conducting silver paint and conductivity (σ) was measured at various constant temperatures (T), ranging from 313-523°K using Digital Picoammeter (ESA 813 Electronics Corporation of India Ltd.). Typical results on potassium niobate is given as plot of log σ against 1/T (Fig. 2).

Seebeck coefficients (α) of the niobates were measured by using a D. C. Microvoltmeter (Philips GM 6020).

Results and Discussion

It was observed that the reactions were almost complete when the mixtures were heated for three hours. Hence subsequently all reactions were carried out for three hours only. When mixtures containing Nb₂O₅ and lithium or potassium carbonate in varying proportions, were heated at high temperatures,

Fig. 2 Plot of log σ vs 1/T for K₂O.Nb₂O₅

various insoluble niobates were formed. Their compositions depend on the proportions of the constituents in the mixtures and the temperature of heating.

It is interesting to note that lithium oxide formed three insoluble niobates, whereas potassium oxide formed only one insoluble niobate. For higher ratios and temperatures the niobates formed were soluble in hot water.

Semiconducting Properties of Niobates :

In Figure 2 logarithm of electrical conductivity (σ) of potassium metaniobate against reciprocal of temperature (T) in °K is shown. The activation energy E_a, for the conduction process was calculated using the equation¹⁸

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 e^{-E_a/kT}$$

where σ is conductivity at T°K, σ₀ is a constant and k is Boltzmann's constant. The slopes of the log σ vs 1/T straight lines were accurately determined using the least square method.

On measuring the electrical conductivity of α, β and γ forms of Nb₂O₅ and also niobates at various temperatures it was observed that conductivity is exponentially dependent on temperature with an activation energy of 0.91 eV in the temperature range of 398-523°K which is in good agreement with the observation of Greener and Hirthe⁹ and 0.14 eV in the range of 313-398°K for α form, 0.95 eV in the range of 413-523°K and 0.21 eV from 313-413°K for β form. On the other hand, γ form has shown only one activation energy that is 1.04 eV. The activation

energies for niobates and different forms of Nb_2O_5 are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ACTIVATION ENERGIES

Sl. No.	Compound	E_a in eV
1.	$\alpha\text{-Nb}_2\text{O}_5$	0.91
2.	$\beta\text{-Nb}_2\text{O}_5$	0.94
3.	$\gamma\text{-Nb}_2\text{O}_5$	1.04
4.	$\text{Li}_2\text{O.Nb}_2\text{O}_5$	1.45
5.	$2\text{Li}_2\text{O.Nb}_2\text{O}_5$	1.24
6.	$3\text{Li}_2\text{O.Nb}_2\text{O}_5$	1.15
7.	$\text{K}_2\text{O.Nb}_2\text{O}_5$	0.97

In all the cases a common feature in the variation of electrical conductivity with temperature is that conductivity first remains constant over certain range of temperature and then it increases rapidly. The ranges over which conductivity remains constant are 313-473°K, 313-433°K, 313-353°K and 313-333°K for lithium meta-, pyro-, ortho- niobates and potassium meta-niobate respectively.

The Seebeck coefficient (α) measurements showed $\text{Li}_2\text{O.Nb}_2\text{O}_5$ and $\text{K}_2\text{O.Nb}_2\text{O}_5$ to be *n*-type and $2\text{Li}_2\text{O.Nb}_2\text{O}_5$ and $3\text{Li}_2\text{O.Nb}_2\text{O}_5$ to be *p*-type.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the authorities of Birla Institute of Technology and Science, Pilani for providing necessary facilities and to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi for the award of a fellowship to one of them (SKA).

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